

CULTUROLOGY

EATING METAPHORS IN ENGLISH AND HEBREW

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ABSTRACT

The paper's aim was to identify, analyze, classify, and compare about 145 English and Hebrew eating metaphors (EM), about 80 English and 65 Hebrew, for the investigation of a general attitude to food and eating, and understanding of the national values of every linguistic community. The investigation of this cultural phenomenon is important for multicultural communication because the contrastive research of English and Hebrew EM is in the beginning. The pilot and limited study corpus consist of various forms of figurative language. Four tables (eating equivalents on the physical and other perspectives, and ethnocultural metaphors in every language) presented the work results. To analyze a large number of equivalent and less numerous ethnocultural food metaphors, Newman's scheme that divided food metaphors into agent-oriented (substances) and patient-oriented (eater) was used. Ancient metaphors talk about the physical value of food for a person, which must necessarily be supplemented by spiritual satisfaction, and the most important conceptual metaphors are the blessing on bread and food in Hebrew and English. Newer metaphors speak of a rational attitude toward the enjoyment of food, which should not be made the goal of life. Hebrew ethnocultural metaphors emphasize the psychological problems of hunger, the need for planning and foresight in preparing meals, English metaphors reveal a connection between efforts to obtain food and rewards for it, and are often pragmatic in nature, describing the setting of goals and the sequence of actions to achieve it.

Keywords: English, Hebrew, eating metaphors, ethnocultural, multicultural communication.

Food is any substance consumed by the body to provide energy, sustain life, or stimulate growth, so every living thing, from algae to whales, needs food to survive according to Maslow's pyramid, food is the basic need and the engine and source of metaphorical meanings in English (Newman, 1997) as well as in Hebrew.

A metaphor is considered to be an embodied physical experience (sensory and motor systems) that shapes our mental experience (Lakoff & Johnson, 1980; Lakoff, 1999). The figurative language of a community can be seen as a reflection of that community's traditional patterns of thought or worldview (Lakoff, 1987, p. 295). While primary metaphors are based on general physical experience, complex experiential areas are more culturally dependent and thus vary from place to place. Conceptual metaphor aims to explain abstract phenomena that are difficult to grasp in simpler language, and the overall advantage of using the concept of metaphor is that it provides motivation and coherence for entire clusters of figurative idioms (Boyer, 2003, 232–235).

Humanities and social sciences scholars are increasingly considering food and drink as building blocks in the creation and reproduction of local, regional, national cultures and identities in Europe (Wilson, 2006, 11) because food metaphors contain important information about practical, cultural, spiritual, linguistic traditions and values. Thus, cultural aspects are fundamental to the characterization of metaphorical systems (Barcelona & Soriano, 2004, 306).

In the age of globalization, which has expanded intercultural contacts and communication, there is an urgent need to include cultural awareness as an integral

part of the culture in the foreign language curriculum (Byram, Nichols, & Stevens, 2001, 236).

The 21st century featured intensive linguistic research on European and non-European food metaphors and food concepts. Between published food metaphors research in one language, it is a must to note the book "Food and Drink Idioms in English" by Laura Pinavaia (2010, 2018). To the study of different languages contributed articles on Arabic (Berrada, 2007); Mandarin, and Shanghainese (Ye, 2010); Portuguese (Monteiro, 2011); and Persian (Khajeh, Z., & Imran-Ho, 2012). These studies usually analyze several or numerous lexemes such as milk and butter from a perspective of quantity, frequency, features of use, and linguistic characters.

Nowadays are very intensive food metaphor contrastive studies in English and other languages are nowadays widespread: e.g. French, German, and Spanish (Pinavaia, 2015); Romanian (Ionesco, 2017); Croatian (Majic, 2017); Spanish (Negro, 2019); Thai (Boontam, 2019) and Hebrew (Kigel, 2022a, 2022 b, forthcoming). Furthermore, contrastive studies dedicated to different languages such as Afrikaans and Northern Sotho (Taljad, Bosman, 2014); Portuguese, Spanish and Chinese (Monteiro et al., 2018); Russian and Italian (Pomarolli, 2021). These studies usually focused on the similes, and differences in the use of the most popular lexemes.

The investigation of bread idioms in English, Russian and Italian (Yurina et al., 2017), and their biblical symbolism in Russian and Italian (Yurina & Pomarolli, 2017) proved the big similarity of figurative language. The deep analysis of fruit as a source and a domain of varied metaphors deed in several papers (Pamies, 2011,

2014, 2015). The recognition of the similar value of cassava, bread, and rice in different cultures based on linguistics, is the theme of special work (Monteiro et al., 2018). Our works are dedicated to food metaphors with the names of edible plants and bread and milk in English and Hebrew (Kigel, 2022a, 2022 b, forthcoming).

Newman's pioneering study (1997, 214) is the only work, as we know, on the global attitude to eating and it focused on a broad category of verbal concepts related to eating and drinking and emphasized the richness of conceptual juxtapositions between the food and drink domain and other domains, rather than documenting the metaphorical use of specific verbs to eat and drink. This paper (Newman, 1997, 214) described the process of eating as consisting of two completely different kinds: interiorization (from the point of view of the nourishing substance), and destruction and removing an entity's internalized imagery (from the eater's point of view) and that the procedure of an agent-centered eating procedure seemed so: intake-mastication - swallowing-digestion - removal from the body, and as a result the disappearing of processed food. Following Newman, it is a slow process, resulting in the disappearance of processed food. A patient-centered procedure seemed different: hunger - intake - mastication - swallowing - digestion - nourishment - enjoyable gustation.

Since the investigation of unrelated and structurally distant languages such as English and Hebrew and food figurative language one of the most acute problems of intercultural communication and modern linguistics, this pilot article aim is to identify and study English and Hebrew eating metaphor (EM) for investigation a general attitude to food and eating, understanding of national values through a material, physical, social, emotional, spiritual, and moral perspective. The investigation of this cultural phenomenon is important for multicultural communication because, in Israel, Hebrew is the state language, and English is very widespread but the because the contrastive research of English and Hebrew food Metaphors is in the beginning.

The results of the study are relevant for comparative and contrastive linguistics, ethnolinguistics, and the theory of intercultural communication, and in practice can be useful in lexicography, including phraseology, and corpora, teaching L2.

Method The study corpus is about 145 (80 English and 65 Hebrew) metaphors as idioms, phraseological and paremiological units, set expressions, proverbs, maxims, and sayings collected from electronic explanation and phraseologic dictionaries, and Internet search. The Lakoff theory of conceptual metaphor and Newman's ideas about food metaphor are at the base of this study.

2. Results

The study results are presented in Table 1 English and Hebrew Metaphors on Physical Perspective of Eating, Table 2 English and Hebrew Equivalent Eating Metaphors, Table 3 Hebrew ethnocultural Eating Metaphors, and Table 4. English ethnocultural Eating Metaphors.

3. Discussion

3.1 Hebrew and English Equivalent Eating Metaphors

English and Hebrew metaphors show the relationship between physical food and the process of satiation from different points of view. For example, the main groups of foods that should be consumed every day (food pyramid); healthy food (whole foods) versus unhealthy food (fast food, junk food). You cannot hold a cake and eat it at the same time, this statement corresponds to the position of scientists that food is destroyed and disappears in the body as a result of eating (Newman, 2009). The metaphor food chain describes a pathway of energy and nutrients through the ecosystem and the food pyramid represents the basic food groups. English and Hebrew metaphors express an attitude to physical food and the satiation process from different perspectives e.g. metaphor food chain describes a pathway of energy and nutrients through the ecosystem, idiom food pyramid - the main groups of foods consumed every day; healthy food (whole foods) versus unhealthy food (fast food, junk food). The scientist's note that food is destroyed and disappears in the body as a result of eating (Newman, 2009) corresponds to the saying you cannot hold a cake and eat it at the same time. The optimal general attitude towards food defines the saying is to eat to live, not live to eat attributed to many famous people. Its meaning is: the eating aim is obtaining energy for action and achieving goals, but enjoyable gustation and satiety can not be the life purpose.

The figurative language usually uses the comparison with animals to describe the exterraging hunger: hungry as a bear, hog the wolf and an opposed to it is a healthy appetite and a hunger strike as a method of non-violent resistance because malnutrition is a way to death. Metaphors describe a small amount of eating food (eat like a bird) in opposite to a big one (eat like a horse, eat for England, eat for two).

Food intake has some minimal limits (bread and water), but there is no metaphor for maximal limits although excessive food consumption for pleasure can lead to health problems. However, food abuse is discussed in the metaphor: eat, drink and be merry, for tomorrow we die is evidence of doubt about the future: if you don't know how many years you will live, so enjoy momentary pleasure. The nowadays principle eat all-you-can-eat also suggests moderation and prudence. The abuse of hospitality (eating out of the house and home), quick eating (wolf food down), and lack of manners (eating like a pig) were condemned also. Exterraging eating because of emotional and physiological needs signed by metaphors comfort food and convenience food.

Humans need food to survive, it is a very important being part but emotional, and spiritual human needs are also very strong: man does not live by bread alone (Tanakh), bread, and circus (Juvenal). It is a must to note that the Tanakh or Hebrew Bible is the main sacred book of Judaism, written in Hebrew and Aramaic and completed in 450 BCE. Christian Bible contains both the Old Testament based primarily upon the Tanakh and New Testaments written in the Koine

Greek language described Jesus and the beginning of Christianity(Definition of Bible).

Following the Tanakh, for achieving food person need to work hard: in the sweat of thy face shalt (God's curse of humans during the expulsion from the Garden of Eden); but at the same time those who make efforts to achieve it, food is guaranteed (עובד אדמתו ישבע לחם) works his land will be fed bread).

The Hebrew metaphor אוכל הינם (freeloader), and the English one the bread of idleness condemn parasitism and exploitation of those that get food and share it with others for humane reasons.

In its turn, the English saying There is no such thing as a free lunch in categorical and pragmatic form declares the universal principle of human society: getting food and other goods is energy embodied in different forms and depends on human efforts. The saying Only free cheese is in the mousetrap emphasizes the dangerousness of manipulation or exploitation that lurks in a supposedly free product.

A popular Hebrew saying performs that preparing meals and eating is a long complex process that needs planning and punctuality(מי שטרחה בערב שבת יאוכל בשבת) he who worked Friday evening, will eat during Shabbat) because according to Jewish custom, all preparations for Saturday must be completed in the evening on the eve of Saturday because Saturday is a holiday day, it is forbidden to buy, prepare food and to work at all.

Bread> living, the most urgent physical person needs bread and water

Bread> a livelihood for a family bread and butter, bread and meat, breadwinner, לחם הרוק.

Bread> wellness, plenty breadwinner; bring home bread and butter.

Bread> wealth, making money bread, heavy bread. It is a modern extension.

Bread> advantages, benefits to have bread buttered on both sides; know on which side your bread is buttered; bread always falls on the buttered side; the best thing since sliced bread.

The absence of bread > poverty below the breadline, take the bread out from people's mouths

Hunger >poor quality from hunger.

Bread is a common main ingredient in every meal. Symbol meanings of bread metaphors are the focus of our article on English and Hebrew Bread and Milk Metaphors (Kigel, 2022b, forthcoming). Bread is the cognitive metaphor for the most urgent physical person's need as food for life, wealth, and plenty contrary to hunger, and poverty (bring home bread and meat, below the breadline).

Due to its great importance in the daily diet, bread has become a symbol of basic and essential things that is impossible without it. In the Torah, Adam was told: "By the sweat of your nose you shall eat bread...", that is, the person has to put in a lot of effort to earn his bread for a living. According to the proverb Man shall not live by bread alone, food, money, and possessions are not enough for man to be happy, he also needs other things, such as culture and art, to enrich his world.

Two language cultures are associated bread (the universal food conceptual metaphor) with life and the Creator based on the idea that the human body and the

land are given by the creator and under his care. Religious Jewish eaters tell the gratitude of the Creator for food at the beginning and end of every meal (המוציא לחם מן הארץ, the one who brings bread out of the land; ברכת המזון, food blessing) and Christian prayers ask Lord to give daily bread.

The Hebrew complex metaphor המוציא לחם מן הארץ (the one who brings bread out of the land) expresses a complicated universal meaning by a number of metaphors: The one - Creator, bread - food, brings out of the land - agriculture work.

The Christian Bible metaphor break the bread means to share a meal is a symbol of hospitality (a bread-and-butter letter); friendliness and informality. The demonstration of faith in Jesus while eating blessed oblates and wine in the eucharist ceremony is based on the Biblical metaphor Eat me drink me. Nowadays bread symbolizes making money and providing a livelihood for the family(breadwinner, bread and butter).

According to G. Lakoff, conceptual metaphors consist of the source domain from which we draw metaphorical expressions (e.g., love is a journey) and the target domain that we try to understand.

Following food metaphors are presented as the source and target domains.

Hunger, big appetite > an intense desire, yearning, or need to continue the action hungry for, go hungry, hunger after, with the food comes the appetite. This metaphor treats physical food and psychological aspects of human behavior.

Eating> the process of thinking intellectual hunger, food for thought. As in Newman's scheme, the thinking process can be described by putting together the stages of an agent-oriented and a patient-centered procedure: hunger - intake- processing- nourishment - enjoyable enjoyable gustation.

Eating>regretting eat your heart out, eat himself. In this case, eating such food instead of pleasure brings suffering, and not pleasure from eating. Newman noted that the idea of torment, suffering, is usually a continuous process or state, rather than a momentary one, and is centered on the agent and the patient.

Eating>criticizing, negative attitude toward another person eat him for breakfast, אכל ארץ אוכלת יושביה, אכל, a land eats its inhabitants or difficult country to live it. Following Newman, it is a slow process of destroying oneself or the other person's reputation in the sense of harming it. These metaphors emphasize the destruction of the moral value and reputation of the criticized person as a result of criticism (the disappearance of food at the end of the process) a gradual destruction similar to the metaphorical extensions of chewing verbs.

Eating non-edible food > difficulties, suffering eat it, לאכול הצץ, לאכול קש. In this situation, inedible food turns eating into an unpleasant process.

Eating non-edible food > publicly admission a humiliating mistake eat hat, crow, לאכול את הכובע

Bad food> negative results of human behavior אכל פרי מעלליו, he ate the fruit of his deeds).

3.2 Hebrew and English Ethnocultural Eating Metaphors

Popular Hebrew ethnocultural metaphors for food draw our attention to additional aspects of food. reveal additional nuances of the relationship to food.

Hunger > negative emotions for a needy person מבייש רעב shameful hunger. The need to ask for food from another person causes a person suffering and humiliation הרפת רעב, shameful hunger.

moderate consumption of pleasant food > moderation in behavior, the desire to avoid exaggeration in everything.

Eating > emotional satisfaction שביעת רצון satisfaction that corresponds to the stage.

Moderate eating of pleasant foods > moderation in deeds, need to avoid exaggeration in anything.

to appetite > the cause of converting religion for sake of comfort and benefits מומר להאבון, converted to appetite ironic.

English Ethnocultural cognitive metaphors many times featured pragmatic connotations:

eating > the result of consistent targeted actions and efforts he that would eat the fruit must climb the tree; he that would eat the kernel must crack the nut; how do you eat an elephant? One bite at a time.

Hunger > a cause of angry, volatile behavior.

Eating > sex high sex appetite, to eat to crave sex. Sex is presented as a long process similar to digestion: Eating - thinking and sex have some similar stages: hunger-doing sex- nourishment- enjoyable gustation.

In addition to various unrelated topics, many English food metaphors are pragmatic in nature and describe setting goals and the sequence of actions to achieve them.

4. Conclusion This study presents both equivalent and ethnocultural food metaphors in English and He-

brew, using Newman's scheme of analyzing food metaphors as agent-centered (substance) and patient-centered (eater). A large number of equivalents in two languages proves a correlative attitude to food. Both the cognitive metaphor Eating is the result of human effort and also the mega metaphor Bread have plenty of various meanings.

Ancient metaphors talk about the physical value of food for a person, which must necessarily be supplemented by spiritual satisfaction, and the most important conceptual metaphors are the blessing on bread and food in Hebrew and English. The most minimal food (bread and water), difficulties in growing agricultural products, obtaining food, and cooking were discussed in figurative language. In the same way, they condemn laziness, idleness, and parasitism.

Newer metaphors speak of a reasonable attitude towards the enjoyment of food, which should not be made the goal of life, and the need for moderation in it, as in other areas of life.

While Jewish ethnocultural metaphors emphasized the psychological problems of hunger and the need for planning and foresight in food preparation, English metaphors found a connection between food, the effort to obtain it, and the reward for it. In addition to various unrelated topics, many English food metaphors are pragmatic in nature and describe setting goals and the sequence of actions to achieve them.

Future research directions are English and Hebrew metaphors for cake and honey, as well as food metaphors in other languages. It is very useful to conduct a study of the frequency of the use of metaphors, a diachronic study, and to illustrate the points of the article with quotations from the literature.

Table 1.

English and Hebrew Eating Metaphors from the Physical Perspective

Food chain a possible pathway that energy and nutrients can follow through the ecosystem, describing who eats whom in the wild.	שרשרת המזון
food pyramid a representation of the optimal number of servings to be eaten each day from each of the basic food groups: Fruits, Vegetables, Grains, Protein Foods, and Dairy	פירמידת המזון
whole food, healthy food processed, refined or had ingredients added to them. Whole foods include fruits, vegetables, legumes, nuts, seeds, whole grains, meat, fish, and eggs. Fruit, vegetables, legumes (e.g. lentils and beans), nuts, and whole grains (e.g. unprocessed maize, millet, oats, wheat, and brown rice) fast food mass-produced foods, frozen, reheated or pre-cooked to take away. junk food high in calories from sugar and/or fat, and possibly also sodium, but with little dietary fiber, protein, vitamins, minerals, or other important forms of nutritional value	מזון בריא מזון מלא מזון מהיר ג'אנק פוד אוכל-זבל
eat to live, not live to eat eating needs to supply health but not be a favorite activity	לאכול כדי לחיות, לא לחיות כדי לאכול
Bread and circuses gaining public approval through superficial means such as diversion and distraction to hide fundamental flaws in society Jubanellis, a Roman poet and satirist 1st century BC	לחם ושעשועים
Eat, drink, and be merry, for tomorrow we die You only live once, so enjoy life	אכול ושתה, כי מחר נמות פסוק, ישעיהו כב יג
bread and water the most minimal meal	לחם ומים
All-you-can-eat people can serve themselves as much food as they want at a restaurant	אכול כפי יכולתך
a healthy appetite a strong interest in and desire to eat well	תאבון בריא
hungry as a bear, as a hog hungry as a hunter be so hungry (that) (one) could eat a horse, be hungry like the wolf	רעב כמו זאב
eat like a bird vs to eat like a horse, eat for England eating very less vs eating much	לאכול כמו ציפור אכל בכל פה
<i>eat for two</i> pregnant woman <i>eat out of house and home</i> consuming so much of someone's store of food that little or none is left for the owner	לאכול בשביל שנים
wolf food down Eating a lot very quickly eat like a pig	אכל כמו חזיר
Emotional eating overeating using food to make yourself feel better—to fill emotional needs, rather than your stomach. you also feel guilty for Comfort food, convenience food a dish that's high-carb, high-sugar, or high in fatty acids—think French fries, cheeseburgers, ice cream, candy, and chocolate	אוכל מנחם
A bout of hunger eager to make money. ambitious	התקף רעב
A hunger strike a method of non-violent resistance in which participants fast as an act of political protest, or to provoke a feeling of guilt in others	שביטת רעב
You cannot have your cake and eat it Once the cake is eaten, it is gone; impossible to have or do two good things at the same	לאכול את העוגה, ולא שאיר אותה, שלמה

Table 2.

Hebrew and English Equivalent Eating Metaphors from Different Perspective

English	Hebrew
<i>bread and water</i> the most minimal meal A meager diet that is barely enough to sustain life	לחם צר ומים לחץ ישעיהו ל כ <i>Narrow bread and pressed water</i>
<i>Man does not live by bread alone</i> people have spiritual as well as physical needs Bread and circuses gaining public approval through superficial means such as diversion and distraction to hide fundamental flaws in society Jubanellis, a Roman poet and satirist 1st century BC	לא על הלחם לבדו יחיה האדם דברים ח, ג לחם ושעשועים
<i>bread and butter, bread and meat, bread winner</i> basic livelihood, in the amount sufficient for a person's living, main income money below the breadline the poverty line breadwinner main earner in a family	לחם חוק
<i>In the sweat of thy face shalt thou eat bread</i> he will have to work for living, Adam's punishment for eating fruit in Eden.	בזעת אפך תאכל לחם פסוק יז, בראשית ג אוכל חנם <i>to live or eat at the expense of others freeloader</i>
<i>Works his land will be fed bread</i> Guaranteed the fruits of the man invested his efforts, the means to advance any cause	עובד אדמתו ישבע לחם פסוק יא, משלי יב
There is no such thing as a free lunch nothing can be received without a price, every act or product has a price, even if it is not visible to the eye. originates in English, the initials of its various versions are also common. TNSTAAFL, TANSTAAFL, TINSTAAFI	אין ארוחות חנם
the only free cheese is in the mousetrap Nothing is truly free, everything comes with conditions, however hidden or unseen. Things without clear motivation are suspect manipulative or to be dangerous.	גבינה חנם יש רק במלכודת עכברים
Let them eat cake disregard or cynical attitude to the starving people Marie Antoinette phrase, the last Queen of France before the French revolution	אם אין לחם תאכלו עוגות
He ate the fruit of his deeds A person bears the consequences of his actions The children's teeth are darkened from unripe fruits that the fathers ate Punishment of descendants for the ancestors' sins ate the porridge he cooked Person pay for his mistakes	אכל פרי מעלליו אבות אכלו כסר ושני בנים תקחינה 'ספר ירמיהו פרק ל"א אכל את הדייסה שבישל
eat the meat and spit out the bones Exploration of good, useful things, and getting rid of the bad	תוכו אכל קליפתו זרק בבלי, דף טו, עמוד ב – מסכת חגיגה <i>Inside he ate and a peel threw away</i>
hungry for (something) having a strong appetite for a particular kind of food The desire or need to feel spiritual fulfillment in one's life. go hungry To remain determined, competitive, motivated, and active in one's hopes, ambitions hunger after, hunger for an intense desire, yearning, or need for something	רעב ל(משהו)
Heart hunger emotional hunger The feelings of weakness, restlessness and frustration vs stomach hunger (physical or medical necessity to eat)	רעב נפשי, רעב רגשי

With the food comes the appetite Starting an activity increases one's desire to continue it. the more you have and the more you want to have	עם האוכל בא התאבון
eat your heart out regretted or suffered eat himself sorry, Repent eat (away) at (someone's) conscience feelings of guilt, especially for an extended period of time. איסורי מצפון	אכל את הלב אכל את עצמו
Eat him alive eat somebody alive angry criticizing to completely destroyed or defeated someone Eat it without salt Defeated him easily Eat someone for breakfast	אכל אותו חי אכל את זה בלי מלח לאכול מישהו חי
eat gravel, straw Suffer eat it He was damaged, injured	אכל חצץ, קשאכל אותה איתה אכל
eat hat /crow/ humble pie/dirt/ eat the frog, publicly admitted humiliating mistake	לאכול את הכובע
food fight a form of chaotic collective behavior when food is thrown for amusement	מלחמת אוכל
worm food corpses in a state of decay; remains	מזון לתולעים
the paper feed a device for inserting sheets of paper into a printer or typewriter feed The part of a machine, that supplies the material to be operated upon.	הזנת הנייר
Food for thought An idea that makes you think seriously	מזון למחשבה
Simulated hunger, unnecessary eating because of the appearance of the food.	לאכול עם העיניים
sexuality. We see this in (3), which is naturally understood to mean that the man wanted to have sex with the woman	לאכול אותה בעיניים

Table 3.

Hebrew Ethnocultural Eating Metaphors

the one who brings bread out of the land blessing on the bread before a meal where bread is eaten	המוציא לחם מן הארץ
The blessing of the food a final blessing that is said according to the Torah, Halacha at the end of every meal	ברכת המזון ספר דברים פרק ח, 'פסוק י'
He who worked Friday's evening, will eat during Shabbat	מי שטרח בערב שבת יאכל בשבת
The honey you find eat moderately It is not good to overdo also in good actions.	דבש מצאת אכל דרך חגיגה יד ב
a land eats its inhabitants a difficult country to live	ארץ אוכלת יושביה במדבר יג לב
converted to appetite committing a crime or converting his religion for pleasure and benefit	מומר לתאבון
ashamed hunger Suffering and humiliation when asking for bread from others	חרפת רעב רעב מבויש יחזקאל לו 30
eater free food parasite	אוכל חינם
main food groups The macronutrients carbohydrates, fats, proteins, vitamins and minerals. are necessary for the proper functioning of the human body	אבות המזון
Ate every mouthful Gobble	אכל בכל פה

Emotional satisfaction	שביעות רצון
	לגזוע ברעב starving
Annoying, disturbing, talks a lot which apparently indicates wisdom and education	אכל את הראש

Table 4.

English Ethnocultural Metaphors

<i>daily bread</i> Matthew 6:11; Luke 11:3 livelihood
<i>Eat me drink me</i> John 6:54 The Jesus saying, the person who draws on, claims, or lays hold of the reality of his atoning sacrifice by putting personal faith in him.
<i>to break the staff of your bread</i> Leviticus 26:70)welcome, of openness, a gesture signifying peace
<i>eat the bread of idleness</i> Proverbs 31 verse 27 a lazy , eat food that one has not personally earned
<i>you eat with your eyes first</i> The sight, odor, taste and even the sound of food all factor in one's decision to choose to eat a certain food.
<i>You do not notice your hunger when you are sleeping.</i> Getting a healthy amount of sleep per night is essential to feeling less hungry.
<i>a hungry man is an angry man</i> the state of anger people feel when hungry
<i>Do you eat with that mouth?</i> Used to chastise someone who is using lewd, vulgar, or obscene language.
<i>a hungry belly has no ears</i> a hungry person not being able to concentrate on anything else
<i>hunger is the best sauce</i> Food tastes better when one is hungry.
<i>from hunger</i> Of very poor quality; terrible. Not very good, interesting, or appealing.
<i>he that would eat the fruit must climb the tree</i> <i>he that would eat the kernel must crack the nut</i> <i>the cat would eat fish, but would not wet her feet</i> In order to enjoy something, you should make first the effort to win it.
<i>don't make yourself a mouse, or the cat will eat you</i> If you belittle yourself, people will take advantage of you
<i>How do you eat an elephant? One bite at a time.</i> To do something one step at a time; to do something in steps rather than all at once
<i>dog does not eat dog</i> disreputable person will not harm other disreputable people <i>Dog-eat-dog world</i> An environment that is ruthlessly competitive
<i>don't know whether to eat it or rub it on food</i> That does not recognize or that looks unusual
<i>Eat high on the hog</i> To live very well and prosper
<i>Eat your heart out!</i> A taunt to indicate that the speaker has outperformed that person in that field
<i>eat my hat</i> something will not happen or cannot be true
<i>Eating out of one's hand</i> To be quite submissive; be manipulated or dominated by another.
<i>Won't eat you</i> no reason to be afraid of one; someone should not be shy about approaching or talking to one
<i>high sex appetite</i> A high sex drive
<i>to eat to crave sex</i> Seven foods packed with nutrients can perk up libido and improve overall health.

References

1. Boers, Frank(2003) 'Applied Linguistics Perspectives on Cross-Cultural Variation in Conceptual Metaphor', *Metaphor and Symbol*, 18: 4, 231 — 238
2. To link to this Article: DOI: 10.1207/S15327868MS1804_1
3. Newman, J.(1997.) *Eating and Drinking as Sources of Metaphor in English*. *Cuadernos de Filología Inglesa* 6, 2: 213-231.
4. Lakoff, G., Johnson, M. (1980) *Metaphors We Live By*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
5. Lakoff, G. (1987) *The death of dead metaphor*. *Metaphor and symbol* 2 (2), 143-147.
6. Lakoff, G., & Johnson, M. (1999) *Philosophy in the flesh: The embodied mind and its challenge to western thought*. New York, NY: Basic Books. Liu, D.-L. (2002).
7. Boers, F. (2003). *Applied Linguistics perspectives on cross-cultural variation in conceptual metaphor*. *Metaphor and symbol* 18 (4), 231 – 238. DOI: 10.1207/S15327868MS1804_1
8. Wilson, T. (2006) *Food, Drink and Identity in Europe: Consumption and the Construction of Local, National and Cosmopolitan Culture*. In: *Food, Drink and Identity in Europe*. Wilson, Thomas, M. (ed). *European Studies* 22, Amsterdam/New York: Rodopi. 11–29.
9. Barcelona A., Soriano C.(2004) *Metaphorical conceptualization in English and Spanish*. *European Journal of English Studies* Vol. 8, No. 3, pp. 295–307 DOI 10.1080/1382557042000277403
10. Byram, M., Nichols, A., & Stevens, D. (Eds.). (2001). *Developing intercultural competence in practice*. Clevedon, Avon, UK: Multilingual Matters.
11. Pinnavaia, L. (2010) *Sugar and Spice... Exploring Food and Drink Idioms in English*. Polimetrica International Scientific Publisher Monza/Italy. Pp. 361.
12. Pinnavaia, L.(2015) *We are what we eat: Analyzing food and drink idioms in English, French, German, and Spanish*. Pp. 465-469.
13. Pinnavaia, L.(2018) *Food and Drink Idioms in English: "A little bit more sugar and lots of spice"*. Cambridge Scholars Publishing, P. 235.
14. Boers, F. (2003) 'Applied Linguistics Perspectives on Cross-Cultural Variation in Conceptual Metaphor', *Metaphor and Symbol*, 18: 4, 231 — 238. DOI: 10.1207/S15327868MS1804_1
15. Boers, F. (2003). *Applied Linguistics perspectives on cross-cultural variation in conceptual metaphor*. *Metaphor and symbol* 18 (4), 231 – 238.
16. Byram, M., Nichols, A., & Stevens, D. (Eds.). (2001). *Developing intercultural competence in practice*. Clevedon, Avon, UK: Multilingual Matters.
17. Berrada, K. (2007). *Food metaphors: A contrastive approach*. *Metaphorik*. de, 13, 1-38. *Khalid Food Metaphors: A Contrastive Approach*. *metaphorik.de* 13/2007
18. Ye, Z. (2010) *Eating and Drinking in Mandarin and Shanghainese: A Lexical-Conceptual Analysis*. In *Proceedings of the 9th Conference of the Australasian Society for Cognitive Science*, 375-383.
19. Monteiro-Plantin, R.(2018) *Gastronomismos lingüísticos: un enfoque fraseológico y . Language Design* 20 (2018: 121-149)).
20. Monteiro, R., Pamies, A., & Lei, C.(2018) "National Culture through its Metaphors: Cassava, Bread and Rice in Brazil, Spain and China". In: Fedulenkova, T. (ed. *Modern phraseology Issues*. Vladimir: Vladimir State University: 98-126.
21. Khajeh, Z., & Imran-Ho, A. (2012). *Persian culinary metaphor: A cross-cultural conceptualization*. *GEMA Onlinetm Journal of Language Studies*, 12(1), 69–87.
22. Ionescu, D. (2017) *Food Idioms and Proverbs in English and Romanian – A Crosslinguistic and Cross-cultural Approach*. Bucharest: OSCAR Print.
23. Majić K.(2017) *Idiomatic expressions associated with the domain FOOD in English and their counterparts in Croatian Osijek*. <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/197875329.pdf>.
24. Negro I. (2019) *Metaphor and Metonymy in Food Idioms*. *Languages*, 4(3), 47; <https://doi.org/10.3390/languages4030047>
25. Boontam, P. (2019) *A Corpus-based Study of Food-related Metaphors in English and Thai*. *The Academic Journal: Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences Nakhonsawan Rajabhat University*, 6(1), 1–43. Retrieved from <https://so05.tci-thaijo.org/index.php/hssnsru/article/view/213048>
26. Kigel T. (2022a) *English and Hebrew Metaphors with Edible Plant(forthcoming)*.
27. Kigel T. (2022b) *English and Hebrew Bread and Milk Metaphors with an edible plant(forthcoming)*
28. Taljard E., Bosman N. (2014) *The Semantics of Eating in Afrikaans and Northern Sotho: Cross-linguistic Variation in Metaphor* *Metaphor and Symbol* 29(3):224-245 DOI:10.1080/10926488.2014.924306
29. Pomarolli G. (2021) *Cultural-Specific and Universal Components of the Russian Food Metaphor in Comparative, Linguistic, Cultural and Lexicographic Aspects*, National Research Tomsk State University. In *Russian*
30. Yurina E., Avramenko O., Pomarolli G. (2017) *The Images of Grain and Bread in Russian, English and Italian Languages: Universal Aspects of Metaphorisation*. *Tomsk State Pedagogical University Bulletin Issue 11 (188)* Pp. 135-139. DOI:1023951/1609-624X-2017-11-135-139
31. Yurina E., Pomarolli, G. (2017) *The biblical symbolism of bread in figurative means of Russian and Italian languages*, 84-106. DOI - 10.17223/19996195/39/6
32. Pamies, A.(2011) *Motivación cultural y botanismos gastronómicos*. In: *Uma (re)visão da teoria e da pesquisa fraseológicas*, Ortiz Alvarez, M.L. and E. Huelva Unterbäumen (Eds.), Pontes/Universidad Nacional de Brasília, Campinas, pp: 49-68.
33. Pamies, A.(2014) *Provérbios fitonímicos e plantas proverbiais*. In: *Fraseologia and Cia: Entabulando diálogos reflexivos*, Silva, S. (Ed.), Pontes, Campinas, pp: 79-104
34. Pamies, A., Lei, C. & Craig, M. (2015) *Fruits are Results: On the Interaction between Universal Archi-Metaphors, Ethno-Specific Culturemes and Phraseology* *Journal of Social Sciences*. DOI:

10.3844/ofsp.10060

37. Definition of Bible. Dictionary.com. www.dictionary.com. Archived from the original on 15 October 2006

38.

39. ממלכת State Bible אתר תנ"ך ממלכת Tanakh website. <https://edu.929.org.il/enrichment/%D7%91%D7%99%D7%AA-%D7%9C%D7%97%D7%9D/>

40. Old and New Testament. OFFICIAL KING JAMES BIBLE ONLINE. <https://www.kingjamesbibleonline.org/>

41. (Wikimilon) ויקימילון

<https://www.google.com/search?q=%D7%95%D7%99%D7%A7%D7%99%D7%9E%D7%99%D7%9C%D7%95%D7%9F&oq=%D7%95%D7%99%D7%A7%D7%99%D7%9E%D7%99%D7%9C%D7%95%D7%9F&aqs=chrome.0.69i59l4j69i61l3.1690j0j7&sourceid=chrome&ie=UTF-8>

42. מילון עברי-עברי מילוג <https://milog.co.il>

43. Idioms and Phrases. The Free Dictionary <https://idioms.thefreedictionary.com/>

44. Merriam-Webster Dictionary. <https://www.merriam-webster.com/>